

**AMERIKA BOLALAR YOZUVCHISI DOKTOR SYUZ ASAR
QAHRAMONLARINING O‘ZIGA XOS XARAKTERLARI VA ULAR
ORQALI YETKAZMOQCHI BO‘LGAN AXLOQIY SABOQLARI**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Amerikalik bolalar adibi Doktor Syuzning eng mashhur asarlari va ularning qisqacha syujeti hikoya qilinadi. Shuningdek har bir asar qahramonlarining ajralib turuvchi jihatlari va bolalar tarbiyasida o‘ziga xos axloqiy saboqlarni nazarda tutishi yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: “Shlyapadagi mushuk” “Fil Xorton” “Loraks” “Grinch” axloqiy saboq.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассказывается о самых известных произведениях американского детского писателя доктора Сьюза и их кратком сюжете. Также выделены отличительные стороны героев каждого произведения и то, что они подразумевают конкретные нравственные уроки в воспитании детей.

Abstract: This article tells about the most famous works of the American children's writer Dr. Seuss and their brief plot. Also, the distinguishing aspects of the heroes of each work and the fact that they imply specific moral lessons in children's education are highlighted.

Kirish. Amerikalik bolalar yozuvchisi Doktor Syuzning haqiqatan ham bolalar adabiyotida beqiyos o‘rni bor. Uning juda ko‘plab hikoyalari nafaqat bolalar qalbidan munosib o‘rin egallagan balki televidenyalarda multifilm shaklida ham

ekranlashtirilgan. Doktor Syuz asarlarining qahramonlari ham noodatiy xarakterlarga ega bo'lib, bolalarga turli xil axloqiy shaklda bilim olishga undaydi.

Muhokama. Doktor Syuzning mashhur asarlari va ularning asosiy qahramonlari haqida quyida tanishib chiqamiz.

“Shlyapadagi mushuk” asarida uzun qizil, oq yo'l-yo'l shlyapa kiygan mushuk bosh qahramon bo'lib u juda ham quvnoq va hazilkash bo'ladi. Doimo Sally ismli qizning uyiga tashrif buyurib, u va uning akasi bilan turli xil sarguzashtlarni boshidan o'tkazadilar. Bu hikoya orqali bolalar muammolarga yechim toppish va mas'uliyatli bo'lish kabi xarakterlarni o'rganishlari mumkin.

“Fil Xorton” hikoyasi qahramoni fil bo'lib u xushmuomala va mehribon. Bu qahramon avvaliga "Xorton tuxumdan chiqadi", keyinroq "Xorton kimni eshitadi!" kabi hikoyalarda ham namoyon bo'ladi. U boshqalar e'tiborsiz qoldirgan kichik jonzotlarni himoya qilishda qat'iyatliliigi va sodiqligi bilan mashhur bo'ladi. Shunday qilib o'zidan kich va ojiz jonzotlarga ham mehribon bo'lish targ'ib qilinadi bu hikoyada.

"Grinch Rojdestvoni qanday o'g'irlagani" filmida Grinch birinchi marta namoyon bo'lgan qo'pol, yashil jonzot. U Rojdestvoni yomon ko'radi va shu sababli uni Huz (Whos) of Huvilli (Whoville) dan o'g'irlashga harakat qiladi, lekin aynan shu jarayonda bayramning asl ma'nosini bilib oladi. Ya'ni aynan bayram arafasida butun oila jam bo'lishi, boshqalarga sovg'a ulashib insonlarning bir-biriga mehr-oqibatni saqlab qolish ham aslida insoniy qadriyat ekanligini anglab yetish mumkin.

"Yashil tuxum va cho'chqa go'shti" hikoyasining doimiy qahramoni Sem bo'lib, u boshqa qahramonni yashil tuxum va go'shtdan iborat noan'anaviy taomni tatib ko'rishga ishontirishga harakat qiladi. U o'zining takrorlanuvchi qofiyalari va qat'iyatliliigi bilan boshqalardan ajralib turadi. Undan aynan boshqalarni ishontirib, ortidan ergashtira olish va qat'iyatlilik xaraterini o'rgansa bo'ladi.

“Loraks” asarida Loraks nomli qahramon daraxtlar manfaati uchun gapiradigan va Truffula daraxtlarini yo'q qilishdan himoya qilishga harakat qiladigan atrof-muhit qo'riqchisi hisoblanadi. . U ekologiya va tabiatni muhofaza qilishning ramzi bo'lib

xizmat qiladi. Aynan shu hikoyada bolalarga atrof muhitni saqlash va himoya qilish ham ezgu insoniy fazilat ekanligi mohirona tushuntirilgan.

Birinchi narsa va ikkinchi narsa: Bu asar qahramonlari "Shlyapadagi mushuk" filmidagi mushuk tashrif buyurayotganda bolalarning uyiga vayronagarchilik tug'diradigan jirkanch qahramonlardir. Ular ko'k sochlari va betartiblikni yaratishdagi roli bilan mashhur. Bu esa o'z navbatida bolalarga saranjomlik va tartib hayotda qanchalik ahamiyatli ekanligini anglatuvchi hikoyadir.

“Toshbaqa Yertl” "Toshbaqa Yertl va boshqa hikoyalar" nomli hikoyada boshqa toshbaqalarni to'plab, o'z qirolligini qurishga harakat qiladigan, kuchga chanqoq toshbaqa hisoblanadi. Hikoya ochko'zlikning zarari va adolatning ahamiyati haqida bolalarga axloqiy saboq beradi.

Bu Doktor Syuz o'zining ko'plab kitoblari davomida yaratgan sevimli qahramonlarning bir nechta misollari edi. Har bir qahramon o'ziga xos shaxsiyatga ega va ular ko'pincha Doktor Syuzning qaysar va xayoliy dunyosiga asoslangan holda bolalarga axloqiy saboq berishni ko'zda tutadi.

Xulosa. Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, Doktor Syuz asarlarida nafaqat umuminsoniy qadriyatlar balki aynan Amerika millatiga xos bo'lgan qadriyatlar ham a'lo darajada singdirilgan. Masalan bolalar o'rganishi nazarda tutilgan to'g'riso'zlik, qat'iytalilik, muammolarga o'zlariga ishongan holda yechim topa olish kabi holatlarni misol keltishimiz mumkin. Bu adabiy asarlar nafaqat bir millat bolalari tarbiyasida balki butun dunyoda bolalar tarbiyasiga ijobiy ta'sir o'tkazishi shubhasizdir.

Adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. "Children's Literature: Approaches and Territories" edited by Janet Maybin and Nicola J. Watson, Bloomsbury Publishing, 2009.
2. "Children's Literature: An Illustrated History" by Peter Hunt, Oxford University Press, 1995.

3. "Children's Literature: Approaches and Territories" edited by Janet Maybin and Nicola J. Watson, Bloomsbury Academic, 2009.

These are just a few examples of the beloved characters that Dr. Seuss created throughout his numerous books. Each character carries a unique personality and often conveys a moral or lesson within the whimsical and imaginative world of Dr. Seuss.

Can you tell me more about the moral or lesson conveyed in "Yertle the Turtle and Other Stories"?

Assistant

Poe

Certainly! "Yertle the Turtle and Other Stories" is a collection of three stories by Dr. Seuss: "Yertle the Turtle," "Gertrude McFuzz," and "The Big Brag." Each story carries its own moral or lesson, but let's focus on the main story, "Yertle the Turtle."

In "Yertle the Turtle," Yertle is a turtle who becomes the self-proclaimed king of the pond. He constantly seeks to increase his power and authority, ordering other turtles to stack themselves up to serve as his throne. As Yertle's stack of turtles grows taller, he becomes more and more tyrannical, disregarding the suffering and discomfort of the turtles beneath him.

The moral lesson conveyed in "Yertle the Turtle" revolves around the theme of power, greed, and the importance of treating others with respect. The story serves as an allegory for oppressive leaders and the dangers of unchecked ambition.

The climax of the story occurs when a plain little turtle named Mack, who is at the very bottom of the stack, decides he has had enough. Mack burps, causing the stack of turtles to collapse, and Yertle's reign comes crashing down. Yertle is humbled, and the other turtles regain their freedom.

The moral of the story is that no one person should have unlimited power and that it is crucial to consider the well-being and rights of others. It teaches the importance of empathy, equality, and standing up against oppression. "Yertle the Turtle" encourages readers, particularly children, to question authority and to value the rights and dignity of every individual.

Dr. Seuss's use of playful language, imaginative illustrations, and memorable characters helps convey this moral lesson in an engaging and accessible way, making it a popular and enduring story in children's literature.